

Two-Stage Machine Learning Approach to Predict the Survival State of Liver Cirrhosis Patients with Correctness Estimates

Ayush Srivastava

ayush25srivastava25@gmail.com

Abstract—Accurate prediction of survival state for liver cirrhosis patients is important for prioritizing liver transplantation. Using a Mayo Clinic study dataset on liver cirrhosis patients, this study aims to utilize clinical measurements to train machine learning (ML) classifiers to predict the patient survival state. Two derived features, logBXProthrombin and logBXCopper combining log(Bilirubin) with Prothrombin or Copper respectively are used for their informativeness for this task. After model evaluations using 20-fold cross validation, the Random Forest (RF) model is chosen for this binary classification task. This RF model achieves a ROC-AUC of 0.83 on a held-out testing dataset. The primary RF model's prediction metrics (deceased class probability, variance, and confidence interval lower bound of the probabilities) are then used to train a secondary ML classifier for estimating correctness of the primary classifier predictions. This secondary ML classifier achieves ROC-AUC = 0.78 and outperforms simple confidence heuristic (ROC-AUC of 0.66).

Index Terms—Liver Cirrhosis, Random Forest Classifier, Machine Learning, Correctness Estimation

1 INTRODUCTION

Liver cirrhosis is a chronic disease affecting millions of people in the United States and the rest of the world. According to The Mayo Clinic¹, cirrhosis occurs due to advanced scarring within the liver, which affects the organ's ability to function properly and leads to liver failure. Furthermore, the National Library of Medicine Duo et al. [2025] states that in 2021, nearly 51 million people in the world were diagnosed with this global disease to various degrees. In 2019, nearly 2 million people had died from Cirrhosis, making it the fifth leading cause of death in the United States for middle-aged adults.

A liver transplant is widely considered the only solution for end stage (terminal) cirrhosis. However, according to The National Library of Medicine Kaplan et al. [2025], liver transplants are extremely expensive and complicated, as patients must be able to obtain matching donors. The total costs associated with a liver transplant often exceed \$1 million. Thus, these liver transplants should be prioritized only for patients most likely to approach death at the earliest. Selecting patients to undergo a liver transplant is an extremely vital and crucial decision that nurses, doctors, and other professionals must make.

However, according to The Health Resources and Services Administration² various medical professionals and doctors often have difficulty in deciding which patients require a liver transplant the most. This leads to an increase in deaths due to inefficient patient selection, as some may be closer to death than professionals realize. According to the Department of

Surgery of the University of California San Diego³, nearly 1,400 people die while waiting for a liver transplant.

In this paper, the main contributions are the following:

- 1) Conducting a comprehensive evaluation of machine learning (ML) classifiers to predict the survival state of liver cirrhosis patients.
- 2) Analyzing which factors most strongly impact the machine learning model's prediction on patients' survival state.
- 3) Training and evaluation of a secondary ML classifier to predict the correctness of the primary classifier for confidence estimates.

The secondary ML model adds a correctness or confidence check on the primary model's predictions to warrant further investigation when needed. As will be shown in this study later in Figure 11, this secondary model demonstrates a greater discriminative potential for correct-vs. incorrect predictions compared to a simple confidence heuristic. This two-stage machine learning framework may support exploratory risk stratification and identify cases requiring further clinical review. Moreover, this method is non-invasive, inexpensive, and readily accessible.

2 RELATED WORKS

In Dickson et al. [1989], the primary purpose of the paper is to predict survival rates for patients with liver cirrhosis over time using the Cox regression method.

Similarly, in Fernández-Esparrach et al. [2001] the Cox regression method is also applied to patients with liver

1. <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/cirrhosis/symptoms-causes/syc-20351487>

2. <https://www.hrsa.gov/optn/patients/resources/liver/liver-allocation-faqs>

3. <https://surgery.ucsd.edu/news-events/living-donor-liver-transplant.html>

cirrhosis with ascites.

In Suarez et al. [2008], Child-Pugh (CP) classification and the Model for End-Stage Liver Disease (MELD) scores are shown to be strong factors for the evaluation of liver transplantation for cirrhosis patients. This paper also uses the same continuous/categorical clinical markers to predict the survival state of liver cirrhosis patients as in Suarez et al. [2008]. Since the creatinine marker and liver encephalopathy are not available in this dataset⁴, the MELD Kamath and Kim [2007] and CP scores have not been calculated for comparison purposes.

In Zhang et al. [2026] also, ML-based modeling is used to predict mortality in liver cirrhosis patients. However, the study uses only Logistic Regression models and does not consider other ML models. Similarly, Ghoshal and Das [2008] paper evaluates like in this paper which finds Random forest models to perform better.

Most related work on liver cirrhosis survival state predictions is based on tracking similar clinical markers at different points of time and evaluating individual patient risk. This research paper aims to predict the survival state for a patient based on their current snapshot of clinical metrics at a given time. That is, the dataset⁵ used here contains the initial clinical markers collected for all patients at the time and their final survival states.

Regarding random forests, the variance of leaf predictions has been used as uncertainty measures as in Dutschmann and Baumann [2021]. However, in this paper, different RF prediction metrics are merged in a secondary RF classifier model for correctness modeling.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Dataset

For this paper, the **Liver Cirrhosis Dataset**⁶ from the UCI Machine Learning Repository Fleming and Harrington [2013] was used. This dataset consists of data from the Mayo Clinic study on patients with primary biliary cirrhosis (PBC) performed between 1974 and 1984. The target feature in this dataset is the Status attribute, which takes two possible values: Censored (C) and Deceased (D). The initial dataset consists of data from 293 patients who took part in the trial and have mostly comprehensive data, as shown in Table 1. The dataset corresponds to the initial clinical markers collected for all patients at a given time and their final survival states. This dataset is randomly split into train (75%) and validation (25%) datasets for our experiments. A train-test split of this proportion retains both training efficiency and performance estimation.

The testing dataset consists of 100 patients with 36% in the Deceased class. These patients did not participate in the clinical trial but agreed to record basic metrics and undergo survival tracking. Hence, several of the features are completely missing in this testing dataset. This testing dataset is held out from all model and operating point selections until the final evaluation.

For this paper, the CL class corresponding to patients censored due to liver transplantation is not included for two reasons:

1. Only 19 patients are present in this category in the training and validation sets.
2. This paper evaluates which patients should be considered for liver transplantation based on their prediction of survival state, and therefore patients who have already received transplantation are excluded here.

TABLE 1
Datasets and their class distributions.

Dataset	Total	Censored	Deceased
Training	219	121	98
Validation	74	47	27
Testing	100	64	36

In this paper, the datasets contain 14 clinical features that represent the input features of our machine learning models. These input features with their descriptions are listed in Table 2 and their respective statistics are in Table 3. The features can be grouped into two categories:

- **Numeric features:** Bilirubin, Prothrombin, Cholesterol, Copper, Age, Albumin, SGOT, Alk_Phos, Triglycerides, Platelets, Stage
- **Categorical features:** Edema, Ascites, Hepatomegaly. Edema attribute takes in 3 possible values (N, S, Y) and the other take in two possible values each.
- Features (Spiders, Sex) have not been included in the ML model's inputs since they have been found to be noisy and uninformative for the classification task.

For the training dataset, the following pre-processing steps are performed:

- **One hot encoding:** For the Edema attribute (categorical with 3 values N, S and Y), one hot encoding was performed to replace it with 3 binary attributes.
- **Imputation of missing values:** For missing values, each feature median is used to fill the missing values respectively. The medians from training dataset will be used for missing value imputation in the validation and testing datasets.
- **Standardize dataset:** Each feature is standardized by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance. The standardization from the training dataset is applied to the validation and testing datasets.

Figure 1 shows the cumulative distribution functions for Bilirubin (left) and Prothrombin (right) markers for the Censored (C) and Deceased (D) patients with liver cirrhosis. Bilirubin distributions show distinct separation between the two classes.

These two features were selected for the cumulative distribution functions because the machine learning classifier ranked those two features highest in terms of feature importance.

Based on the cumulative distribution function for bilirubin showing the potential to separate the target classes, two derived features are introduced:

- 1) **logBXProthrombin:** This is computed as the product of Prothrombin and the logarithm-of-bilirubin.

4. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/878/cirrhosis>

5. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/878/cirrhosis>

6. <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/878/cirrhosis>

TABLE 2
14 Clinical features used in the cirrhosis dataset.

Input feature	Description
Bilirubin	Serum bilirubin in [mg/dl]
Cholesterol	Serum cholesterol in [mg/dl]
Prothrombin	Prothrombin time in seconds [s]
Copper	Urine copper in [ug/day]
Age	Age in [days]
Albumin	Albumin in [gm/dl]
SGOT	SGOT in [U/ml]
Alk_Phos	Alkaline phosphatase in [U/liter]
Ascites	Presence of ascites N (No) or Y (Yes)
Hepatomegaly	Presence of hepatomegaly N (No) or Y (Yes)
Edema	Edema presence N (none), S (without diuretics), or Y (despite diuretic therapy)
Platelets	Platelets per cubic [ml/1000]
Stage	Histologic stage of disease (1, 2, 3, or 4)
Triglycerides	Triglycerides in [mg/dl]

TABLE 3
Feature Characteristics - Values reported are mean and (standard deviation).
Testing dataset has 5 numerical features completely missing.

Dataset	Training (n=219)	Validation (n=74)	Testing (n=100)
Age (days)	18466.54 [3991.19]	18515.46 [3458.86]	19519.11 [3519.22]
Bilirubin	3.93 [4.94]	2.88 [3.65]	3.01 [3.86]
Cholesterol	363.91 [229.42]	344.41 [157.82]	-
Albumin	3.53 [0.43]	3.48 [0.40]	3.44 [0.42]
Copper	94.21 [86.74]	100.23 [76.76]	-
Alk_Phos	2060.66 [2244.81]	1866.70 [2052.29]	-
SGOT	121.63 [59.70]	123.35 [51.96]	-
Tryglicerides	122.10 [58.09]	123.22 [71.98]	-
Platelets	256.61 [92.85]	267.76 [103.27]	236.46 [95.06]
Prothrombin	10.77 [1.05]	10.69 [0.94]	10.77 [1.09]
Stage	3.03 [0.88]	2.99 [0.90]	3.00 [0.88]

Fig. 1. Plots showing the cumulative distribution functions for Bilirubin marker (left) and Prothrombin (right) for the censored (C) and deceased (D) patients with liver cirrhosis.

- 2) **logBXCopper**: This is computed as the product of Copper and the logarithm-of-bilirubin.

These features are derived to accentuate the differences between the two survival states in the 1-d density plots for the features of Prothrombin and Copper.

After one-hot-encoding of the Edema attribute and the addition of the above two derived features, the dataset now consists of 18 input features.

Figure 2, is a Pearson correlation matrix that was calculated to explain and analyze the correlations between the different input features. This matrix was developed using the Seaborn library⁷. Cells in lighter colors show positive correlations,

7. <https://seaborn.pydata.org/>

Fig. 2. Pearson Correlation Matrix between the 18 input features

whereas cells in darker colors show negative correlations. Albumin and Edema_0 (corresponding to Edema = N value) are shown to be negatively correlated with most of the other input features.

4 PROCEDURE

In this study, there were four main phases, as shown in Figure 3. These 4 phases are described in detail below.

Fig. 3. Phases in this paper

4.1 Cross validation

In this phase, multiple machine learning (ML) classifiers were evaluated using 20-fold stratified cross-validation with Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Area under the curve (AUC) as the scoring metric on the training dataset. AUC has been shown to be the preferred scoring metric Huang [2005] compared to accuracy in evaluating the predictive capacity of machine learning classifiers. Scikit-learn,⁸ an API library for ML classifiers, was used for this purpose. Table 4 lists the eight different classifiers evaluated along with their AUC scores in descending order.

TABLE 4
ML classifiers evaluated with their cross-validation AUC scores.

ML Classifier Model	AUC
Random Forest (RF)	87.67%
Logistic Regression	87.39%
Linear SVC	86.55%
Naive Bayes	84.00%
Nearest Neighbors	83.32%
QDA	83.31%
AdaBoost	80.07%
Decision Tree	64.70%

The random forest (RF) classifier model (number of estimators = 1000) ranked highest with AUC = 87.67% and was selected as the best model for this dataset and classification task. Logistic Regression achieves comparable AUC (87.39%) to RF (87.67%), suggesting that nonlinear interactions do not provide significant gains.

Random Forest Breiman [2001] constructs an ensemble of decision trees using bootstrap aggregation, which reduces variance and improves generalization. Because decision trees partition the feature space nonlinearly, the ensemble is capable of modeling complex feature interactions present in the dataset. This structural property explains its superior AUC performance (87.67%) compared to the other seven models evaluated.

4.2 Training the primary classifier

The RF classifier model is then trained on the training data set to predict the survival state of liver cirrhosis patients. From the trained RF model, the importances of the features are obtained and are listed in Table 5. The two derived features are of highest importance for this classification task.

8. https://scikit-learn.org/stable/supervised_learning.html

TABLE 5
Features ranked in descending order of RF model importance.

Feature	Coefficient
logBXCopper	0.1486
logBXProthrombin	0.1320
Prothrombin	0.1096
Bilirubin	0.0934
Age	0.0758
Copper	0.0718
Alk_Phos	0.0579
SGOT	0.0578
Cholesterol	0.0492
Albumin	0.0486
Tryglicerides	0.0451
Platelets	0.0415
Hepatomegaly	0.0234
Stage	0.0186
Ascites	0.0142
Edema_0	0.0058
Edema_2	0.0047
Edema_1	0.0019

Feature importance in the RF model reflects the total impurity reduction contributed by each variable across all trees. The log-transformed copper and prothrombin measures ranked highest, indicating that these variables consistently produced the largest reductions in classification impurity. The superior ranking of the log-transformed variables relative to their raw counterparts suggests that the transformation improved class separability, likely by reducing skew and enhancing threshold-based splits. Clinical laboratory markers of hepatic dysfunction (prothrombin, bilirubin, copper) dominated importance rankings, consistent with their direct physiological relationship to liver failure severity and patient survival.

This RF model will be the primary/main classifier in this study and is then used to make predictions on the validation dataset. A Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, depicting the relationship between the True Positive Rate (TPR) vs. the False Positive Rate (FPR) for the entire range of probability scores, is plotted for the predictions of the validation dataset in Figure 4. Here, the Deceased class is treated as the Positive class. The True Positive Rate or Recall is defined as the ratio of the number of true positives (data points predicted correctly) by the model to the total number of positive data points. The False Positive Rate is defined as the ratio of the number of false positives to the total number of negative data points.

From the ROC plot in Figure 4, the optimal threshold = 0.5 is chosen as the operating point of the model, as indicated by the orange dot. This threshold corresponds to TPR = 85.19% and FPR = 17.02% on the validation dataset. This threshold represents a probability value for classifying data points as Deceased with probability score above the threshold and Censored for data points scoring below the threshold. The threshold of 0.5 maximizes the Youden Index⁹ (TPR - FPR), making it the optimal point. Using this threshold, the primary confusion matrix is calculated for the predictions of the RF classifier on the validation dataset, as shown in Figure 5. Confusion matrices are utilized to depict the results of a machine learning classifier by comparing its predicted labels to actual labels. The diagonal

9. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5699226/>

Fig. 4. Primary classifier ROC Curve plotted for the validation dataset predictions (AUC = 0.89)

		Predicted label		Accuracy	83.78%
		Censored	Deceased	Total	Recall
True label	Censored	39	8	47	82.98%
	Deceased	4	23	27	85.19%
Total		43	31	74	
Precision		90.70%	74.19%		

Fig. 5. Confusion Matrix computed from primary classifier predictions on the validation dataset

cells in blue are the number of data points that the model was able to correctly identify as positive or negative, while the off-diagonal cells are the number of data points that the model was unable to correctly predict.

4.3 Training the secondary classifier

In this phase, a secondary RF classifier model is trained to estimate the correctness in the prediction of the primary classifier. For this model, we will use the primary classifier’s cross validation predictions on the training dataset to set the target label as Correct or Incorrect. The target label will be Correct for a training data point if it was predicted correctly by cross validation, else it will be Incorrect.

For this secondary RF model, we will use some metrics from the predictions of the primary RF classifier. These metrics are as follows.

- 1) **Probability of the deceased class (D)**
- 2) **Variance (Var):** Variance of the probability of the deceased class across the probability vectors from the decision trees in the RF.
- 3) **Confidence interval lower bound (CILB):** Lower bound of the 95% confidence interval from the probabilities of the deceased class across the probability vectors of the decision trees in the RF.

In addition to the three metrics above, the other input features for this classifier will be:

- Alk_Phos
- Age
- DXAge (Product of the deceased class probability D and age)

In the training data set, 176 data points were labeled Correct and the remaining 43 are labeled Incorrect as a result

of cross-validation. The objective of this secondary classifier is to predict the correctness of the primary classifier’s prediction as labeled by the target attribute Correct vs. Incorrect.

For the secondary classifier, another RF classifier is trained with shallow trees (number of estimators = 1000, max depth = 3, class weight = balanced). A second ROC plot, shown in Figure 6, depicts the relationship between the True Positive Rate and the False Positive Rate for the secondary classifier. Here, the Correct class is treated as the Positive class.

Fig. 6. Secondary classifier ROC Curve plotted for the validation dataset predictions.

		Predicted label		Accuracy	78.38%
		Incorrect	Correct	Total	Recall
True label	Incorrect	7	5	12	58.33%
	Correct	11	51	62	82.26%
Total		18	56	74	
Precision		38.89%	91.07%		

Fig. 7. Confusion Matrix computed from secondary classifier predictions on the validation dataset

For this classifier, the optimal threshold = 0.48 was chosen as its operating point, as it maximized the Youden Index. This corresponds to a True Positive Rate of 82.26%, False Positive Rate of 41.67% and F1 = 86.44%. Using this threshold, the second confusion matrix is calculated for the secondary RF classifier’s predictions in the validation dataset, as shown in Figure 7.

4.4 Evaluations on testing dataset

The testing dataset consists of data from 100 patients, but with several features (7 out of 14 clinical features) that are completely missing, as listed in Table 6. Simple imputation using feature medians from the training data set was used.

The primary and secondary classifier models are now used to make respective predictions on the held-out testing dataset.

All of the code was developed in Python on Google’s Colab notebook and is available on GitHub¹⁰.

10. <https://github.com/Armoredpawn/Liver-Cirrhosis-Survival-State-Prediction>

TABLE 6
Features completely missing in testing dataset.

Missing features
Copper
Alk_Phos
SGOT
Cholesterol
Triglycerides
Hepatomegaly
Ascites

5 RESULTS

A confusion matrix was created to depict the results based on the predictions of the primary RF classifier on the testing dataset, as shown in Figure 8. This is computed using the primary RF classifier threshold as set in Phase 2. By accurately predicting 72 of the 100 data points, the primary Random Forest classifier achieved an overall accuracy of 72.00%, a TPR of 58.33%, and a FPR of 20.31%. For baseline purposes, a default classifier (predict Deceased) would have achieved an accuracy = 36% and Deceased class precision = 36% too.

		Predicted label		Accuracy	72.00%
		Censored	Deceased	Total	Recall
True label	Censored	51	13	64	79.69%
	Deceased	15	21	36	58.33%
Total		66	34	100	
Precision		77.27%	61.76%		

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix computed from primary classifier predictions on the testing dataset

Table 7 shows the primary RF classifier performance metrics on the validation and testing datasets.

TABLE 7
Primary RF classifier performance on validation and testing datasets

Metric	Validation dataset	Testing dataset
Accuracy	83.78%	72%
TPR	85.19%	58.33%
FPR	17.02%	20.31%
F1	79.31%	60%
AUC	0.89	0.83

A MELD-inspired proxy score was constructed using available clinical signals in the dataset, including bilirubin, prothrombin time, and albumin. Due to the absence of creatinine and INR in the data set, this proxy approximates the severity of liver disease, but does **not** represent the clinically validated MELD score Kamath and Kim [2007].

$$MELD_{proxy} = \ln(bilirubin) + \ln(prothrombin) - \ln(albumin) \tag{1}$$

The primary RF classifier model evaluated on the testing data set produces the ROC plot shown in Figure 9. The primary RF classifier obtains an **AUC = 0.83**, while the MELD proxy baseline achieves an **AUC = 0.79**.

A second confusion matrix was created to present the secondary classifier predictions on the testing dataset, as shown in Figure 10 using the respective threshold set before in Phase 3. Here, we can accurately identify the correct

Fig. 9. ROC plot comparing the primary RF classifier-vs-MELD proxy for the testing dataset.

		Predicted label		Accuracy	75.00%
		Incorrect	Correct	Total	Recall
True label	Incorrect	16	12	28	57.14%
	Correct	13	59	72	81.94%
Total		29	71	100	
Precision		55.17%	83.10%		

Fig. 10. Confusion matrix computed from secondary classifier predictions on the testing dataset

predictions with a TPR = 81.94% and precision = 83.10%.

Table 8 shows the secondary RF classifier performance metrics on the validation and testing datasets.

TABLE 8
Secondary RF classifier performance on validation and testing datasets

Metric	Validation dataset	Testing dataset
Accuracy	78.38%	75%
TPR	82.26%	81.94%
FPR	41.67%	42.86%
F1	86.44%	82.52%
AUC	0.68	0.78

A simple probability-based confidence heuristic is defined as:

$$confidence = abs(p - 0.5) \tag{2}$$

where p is the probability of the deceased class from the primary RF model. This confidence heuristic is used as a baseline for confidence estimation, where predictions farther than 0.5 are considered to be more reliable or confident. The secondary RF classifier outperforms this confidence heuristic by achieving **AUC = 0.78** compared to **AUC = 0.66** by the confidence heuristic shown in the ROC graph in Figure 11.

Table 9 lists examples from testing dataset with primary and secondary classifier predictions in last 2 columns respectively. The first 2 rows are examples where the secondary classifier predicts "Incorrect" predictions. These cases warrant further investigation. The last 2 rows are examples where the secondary classifier predicts "Correct" predictions.

TABLE 9
Examples of testing dataset cases with primary and secondary classifier predictions in last 2 columns respectively.
Missing values have been denoted as -

Age	Bilirubin	Albumin	Platelets	Prothrombin	Stage	Target	Predicted	Predicted correct
12419	1.8	3.24	-	18	2	C	D	Incorrect
19724	1	3.6	-	12.1	2	D	C	Incorrect
21915	0.7	3.65	378	11	-	C	C	Correct
23741	1.4	3.04	331	12.1	4	D	D	Correct

Fig. 11. ROC plot comparing the secondary RF classifier-vs-probability based confidence heuristic on the testing dataset

6 DISCUSSION

The results of both primary and secondary ML classifiers demonstrate that the Random Forest-based system shows potential to predict the survival state of patients with liver cirrhosis using non-invasive clinical markers.

On the held-out testing dataset, the primary classifier achieved an accuracy of 72.00%, with a TPR of 58.33% for deceased patients and a FPR of 20.3%. For this testing data set, which has 7 completely missing features and has a baseline accuracy (predict Deceased) of 36%, the primary classifier shows potential for discriminating between high-risk and low-risk patients. The MELD proxy baseline is also a strong contender here (AUC = 0.79) compared to the primary classifier (AUC = 0.83). Again, missing features in the testing dataset make this a harder problem compared to the validation dataset as shown in Table 7 performance metrics.

Several sources of error may have influenced the performance of the model. First, the size of the data set is relatively small, with 293 patients used for training and validation and 100 patients in the testing set, which can limit the statistical power of the model and increase the variance in performance estimates. Second, the testing dataset contained several missing clinical features that required imputation. Finally, the class imbalance between censored and deceased patients can affect performance metrics, particularly accuracy, although the use of ROC-based model selection mitigates some of these effects.

This study also has several limitations. The model was trained and evaluated on a dataset consisting of patients with primary biliary cirrhosis collected between 1974 and 1984, which may not fully represent modern patient populations or other etiologies of cirrhosis such as viral, alcoholic, or nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. The analysis is based on a

binary survival outcome and does not incorporate time-to-event information, which is commonly used in clinical survival analysis. Furthermore, the confidence estimates are derived from variability across decision trees rather than from a fully probabilistic or Bayesian framework and, therefore, represent an approximation of predictive uncertainty rather than a calibrated posterior probability.

This study is exploratory methodological demonstration and not intended for clinical decision-making or deployment without further validation.

7 CONCLUSION

Since the RF classifier had achieved the highest cross-validation AUC, that model was selected as most optimal classifier for this study. Through careful analysis of the Cirrhosis Dataset, two derived features (logBXCopper and logBXProthrombin) were created in addition to the 14 clinical features present. These derived features ranked highest in the RF model's feature importances. This RF model had achieved an AUC = 0.83 and an accuracy = 72.00% on the held-out testing dataset. This primary RF model outperforms a MELD proxy baseline (AUC = 0.79).

A secondary ML classifier is trained to estimate the correctness in the predictions of the primary model. The secondary classifier achieved an AUC = 0.78 and an accuracy = 75.00% to distinguish correct from incorrect predictions, on the held-out testing dataset. By incorporating the predicted probability, variance across decision trees, and the confidence interval lower bound, the secondary classifier estimates which data points have been predicted correctly by the primary model. This is particularly valuable in medical decisions, where the recognition of the uncertainty of a model's output is critical for safe deployment. Rather than relying solely on a single probability score, the proposed approach offers a mechanism to flag predictions that may require additional clinical review.

Some next steps for this paper include training the classifiers on a greater amount of data to improve accuracy and recall. Then, medical professionals will be able to efficiently and accurately predict the survival states of patients with Cirrhosis and facilitate transplants accordingly. Another future goal is to increase the amount of clinical features utilized, in order to increase the model's understanding of a cirrhosis patient's lifestyle and health. Finally, a final potential goal is to evaluate the classifiers on other global cirrhosis datasets, such as Kaggle's cirrhosis dataset¹¹.

11. <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/fedesoriano/cirrhosis-prediction-dataset>

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8 APPENDIX 1

In Figure 12, the 1-d density plots (on diagonal) and 2-d scatter plots for some of the important clinical markers related to Liver Cirrhosis are depicted.

Fig. 12. Scatter and density plots for censored (class 0) and deceased (class 1) patients